

Synthesis Report 8.2: UK Arts & Sports as Resolution Media

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and broader social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) to move towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, including a sense of being victimised, being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. Mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts is crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that radicalisation processes often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national justice frameworks. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation is central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary

This report presents the empirical data which had been collected as a part of the WP8 fieldwork and discuss the empirical findings in relation to the relevant literature. Thus, this report will show (1) how certain sentiments could make individuals vulnerable to radicalised ideologies and behaviours and (2) how non-binary reading of socio-political-cultural identities can tackle feelings of exclusion/alienation. We take radicalisation as an outcome of the breakup of a sense of belonging, and we suggest that arts and sports-related interventions can operate as deradicalization media. Following this approach, WP8 followed individuals' reflections on where they are situated along the I-Gap spectrum in their everyday lives as a proxy for being prone to radicalisation. In response, in 5 countries under the scope of this WP, we have concentrated on sports and arts activities undertaken during the course of 2023 in selected sites to examine how they bolster a sense of belonging thrust by access to shared spaces, where people with different backgrounds could gather around a common interest and tackle the feeling of exclusion thereafter. This is our approach to de-radicalisation in WP8 as well as in D.Rad. We take any type of *othering* by the wider society of the wayward other as an outcome of their being qualified as either belong or not belong in a dichotomised fashion. Therefore, *othering* is a result of a binary reading of identities that also expects first societies to be composed of similar identity groups. In return, we argue that there are gradients of belongingness that can be captured by a "non-binary" focus more fluently. Hence, we advocate the idea that to build more inclusive societies we must reconceptualise the definition of a society with a non-binary understanding. This report develops its arguments on empirical data collected through in-depth interviews and focus groups with the participants of sports and arts activities in Slovenia, Serbia, Israel, Slovenia and the United Kingdom. This report discusses how environments built on interest similarity can break dichotomised belonging, and enhance sense of belonging. Hence, we invite scholars who work on radicalisation and deradicalization to engage more with the mechanisms of othering and social exclusion to facilitate a deeper understanding of these issues.

Table of Contents

<i>About the Project</i>	2
<i>Executive Summary</i>	4
<i>1. Introduction</i>	6
<i>2. Ethics and Equalities Framework</i>	6
<i>3. Protection of Research Participants</i>	12
<i>3. Protection of Researchers</i>	17
<i>4. Human Rights Risks</i>	<i>Error! Bookmark not defined.</i>
<i>5. References</i>	17

1. Introduction

The D.Rad WP8 entitled “Arts and sports as resolution media” examines the transformative power of sports and arts activities in deradicalisation processes. In this effort, project partners organised arts and sports activities in the UK, Serbia, Poland and Israel to evaluate the capacity of such activities as a preventive measure as well as an inclusionary practice. Our intention, in the D.Rad project, is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations. In this report, we will present the empirical data which had been collected as a part of the WP8 fieldwork and discuss the empirical findings in relation with the relevant literature. Thus, this report will show (1) how certain sentiments could make individuals vulnerable to radicalised ideologies and behaviours and (2) how non-binary reading of socio-political-cultural identities can tackle feelings of exclusion/alienation.

The D.Rad project places its I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) at the heart of its approach to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts that drive radicalisation. In relation to that, the D.Rad project takes individuals’ sense of exclusion/alienation as one of the first steps of radicalisation. Such feelings commonly cause isolation for people who are vulnerable to have their sense of belonging thwarted. Their isolation is mostly followed by feelings of injustice, grievance, and alienation - which we consider as elements of the I-Gap spectrum. In this regard, if we take radicalisation as an outcome for the breakup of sense of belonging, then we can also suggest arts and sports related interventions as deradicalization media. As a result of this understanding, the WP8 has focused on individual reflections about how they find themselves along the I-Gap spectrum in their everyday lives. Hence, in 5 countries under the scope of this WP, we have concentrated on sports and arts activities undertaken during the course of 2023 in selected sites to examine how they have bolstered sense of belonging thrust by access to shared spaces, where people with different backgrounds could gather around a common interest and tackle the feeling of exclusion thereafter.

Along with the structural factors that could trigger radicalisation, an imposition by the wider society that there should be some “accepted ways of living” may alienate either those that do not feel that there should or those who do not conform with the accepted ways of living as defined by the wider society. This may indeed raise the grievance felt by the latter two against the wider society affecting their sense of belonging adversely. To our understanding, forcing someone to shed their ways of living so that they can conform with the accepted ways of living of the wider society can therefore be radicalising. Historically, the demands for conformity have defined the non-conforming groups as others inasmuch as they fell out of the expected and accepted ways of living (Anderson 2013). Othering has facilitated the wider societies to ignore the injustices that their systematic others have faced in their everyday. Othering also demoted the importance of struggles that people who fell out of the accepted ways of living would tend to go through. If we take modern societies as a community of values that are populated by people that share similar ways of living and are law-abiding, the unfitting other may stand out as a group of people that have failed to fit into this community considering their different way of living (Anderson, 2013: 3). Those are the wayward other. In the D.Rad project, we take any type of othering by the wider society of the wayward other as an outcome of their being qualified as either belong or not belong in a dichotomised fashion. Therefore,

othering can be a result of a binary reading of identities that also expect first societies to be composed of similar identity groups. This in return thwarts sense of belonging and leads to an increasing appeal of extremist ideas. In return, we argue that there are gradients of belongingness that can be captured by a “non-binary” focus more fluently. Hence, we advocate the idea that to build more inclusive societies we must reconceptualise the definition of a society which provides spaces where “non-binary” belongingness can be actualised instead of dichotomised self vs other identity frames. Using data from the I-GAP Survey, we tried to establish a causal relationship between self-esteem, anomie and extremism. To do so we ran 3 different linear regression models using an extremism scale, calculated from 14 different variables, as the dependent variable. We control for demographics (age and gender) as well as an anomie scale created using 12 different variables and a self-esteem scale, calculated from 4 different variables. We found that people that scored higher on anomie and self-esteem scales are, on average, more prone to express extremist ideas. This result is also true when we include both variables in the same model. We also found women and younger individuals are less prone to extremism. It is good to highlight that the results were computed using the correct variance-covariance matrix clustered by the country of residence to eliminate heteroscedasticity, therefore the results are all robust and valid. This is why we can assume a thwarted sense of belonging as a driver for an increased appeal of extremist ideas.

Arts and sports related interventions give us a way to see how non-binary types of belonging can be experienced and entertained. To break the spell of radicalisation, in the D.Rad project, we reflect on the importance of spaces and activities that people with different backgrounds gather. In this effort, we took participatory arts- and sports-related engagements to tackle feelings of social isolation, disadvantage, and othering. Spaces such as these offer opportunities for greater dialogue and the deconstruction of demonising tropes that continue to frame extremist and radical ideologies. In the following sections, we will discuss how arts and sports activities become manifestations of the non-binary nature of identities and generate *convivial* experiences for the people who take part.

Relatedly, the most striking aspect of the data in our WP8 research was to see how othering triggers similar feelings in people regardless of the way that it is experienced and despite their ethnic, national, gender or religious backgrounds. The collected data contains interviews with three different groups from Poland, the United Kingdom, Serbia, Slovenia and Israel. Research participants both in Poland and the United Kingdom as an example shared the main characteristics of the majority population of their countries. In Poland, our data was gathered from the football fans who were perceived as hooligans by the wider society. In the United Kingdom, interviews involved people who come from disadvantaged backgrounds and who have suffered or already suffering from drug or alcohol addiction. Both in Polish and the UK data, the majority of the interviewees neither had migrant or minority backgrounds nor racial differences, and none of them identified themselves as transgender, gay or non-binary as all these features are among the major exclusion drivers for the wider societies. Interviewees in Serbia, Slovenia, and Israel have either migrant or ethnic minority backgrounds. Hence, we could assume their othering to be more acute and deeply felt. However, our presumption is that they are all othered as they fell out of the expected ways of living by the society. Conceptually, therefore, we can assume that they can become prone to being radicalised as their sense of belonging has been thwarted. Before presenting the findings of the fieldwork, we will discuss the relevant literature to facilitate a deeper understanding of the concepts laid above that will help us in our data interpretation. The methodology for WP8 has been detailed in country reports and the synthesis report uses the same methodological approach.

2. Conceptual Discussion

2.1 Belongingness

In different literature, a sense of belonging is often defined as a positive feeling of being an integral part of one's social and physical environment (Hagerty et al., 1992; Tachine et al., 2017; Mahar et al., 2012). Such definitions capture one of the most fundamental human desires to experience a meaningful connection to one's family, friends, community, cultural groups, and physical environments, which is expected to enhance one's psychological well-being and fulfilment (Strayhorn, 2018; Allen, 2020). Thus, we can say that belonging is related to feelings of safety and a feeling of being understood and accepted within the collective entity (Porter et al., 2021; Wood & Waite, 2011; Antonsich, 2010). Therefore, a sense of belonging is generally taken as a subjective feeling that encompasses community, acceptance, respect, inclusion, identification, or connectedness to a specific context and a group. The traditional concept of belonging can therefore appear rather fixed and linear. Our understanding of the concept of belonging is, however, shaped by politics of belonging literature (Guibernau, 2013; Anthias, 2006; Yuval-Davis, 2006). As such, belonging is perceived as an individual's deliberate claim to acquiring membership of socially constructed collectives resulting in their identification with them. The politics of belonging literature suggest that sense of belonging is a dynamic and evolving phenomenon (Savage et al., 2004; Jones & Krzyzanowski, 2008; Birkner, 2020; Lähdesmäki et al, 2016; Osei-Kofi, 2012). It is continually negotiated and it evolves throughout an individual's lifetime (Afonso et. al., 2022). The resulting fluidity allows individuals to navigate, engage with, and feel a sense of belonging across various socio-cultural and political contexts, relationships, and affiliations over time.

2.2 Alienation, discriminated and marginalisation

Current politics imply a series of disruptions that also polarise societies. As we stated above, the D.Rad project has placed a fractured the sense of belonging as an element of radicalisation and its mend by social inclusion oriented interventions as part of deradicalization processes. That is why we believe that understanding the underlying factors of polarization in societies is important to capture the facilitators of radicalisation as well. We may take such examples as election of Trump or the British vote to leave the EU as polarizing disruptions. Such political incidents can be outcomes of various societal and economic events including the so-called refugee crisis, increased income inequality or even wars in distant geographies. As a result, polarization continues to adversely affects the sense of belongingness of individuals. As we discussed above, belongingness is experienced by the individuals that compose societies and these individuals' socio-political-cultural environments have indisputable effects on one's sense of belongingness. Therefore, political or economic incidents may affect someone's confidence and their perception of missing opportunities. Such feelings could easily trigger a sense of exclusion for those individuals. As a result, these feelings can affect citizens' relationship with their communities or the level of trust citizens have in the institutions governing their lives. As we mentioned above, we elaborate on radicalisation with the guidance of sense of belonging. In this regard, we argue that, if we take belonging as a process that

involves socio-political-cultural processes, then we must consider their influence on exclusion as well as their capacity to strip belongingness of an individual or group.

Powell and Menenian (2016) identify the capacity to “other” by interpreting othering as “a set of dynamics, processes, and structures that engender marginality and persistent inequality across any of the full range of human differences based on group identities”; and clarify that “dimensions of othering include, but are not limited to, religion, sex, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status (class), disability, sexual orientation, and skin tone”. However, othering is a dynamic concept as it is a process that could capture various types of expressions of prejudice towards different groups in societies. Therefore, the *others* of the societies can change in time and context. Powell and Menenian summarise their understating by defining othering as “a broadly inclusive conceptual framework that captures expressions of prejudice and behaviours such as atavism and tribalism, but it is also a term that points toward deeper processes at work, only some of which are captured by those terms”. Haely discusses belonging involving the failure to belong either through the loss of a sense of belonging (not-belonging) or the removal of membership belonging (un-belonging) (Haely, 2020). In our understanding, *othering* could trigger three feelings that are highly related to radicalisation; feelings of alienation; discrimination; and marginalisation. The people who feel any of these may perceive themselves as left behind and some of them may grow hatred towards the wider society and blame it for their exclusion. Polarisation is also highly related to these both as an outcome and a trigger.

We take the feeling of *alienation* as a feeling of isolation from the way everyday sites remain under the spectre of politics. People, who feel alienated mostly suffer from losing connection with the political class and feel that politics is done to them instead of by them. Their disconnection to the socio-political life of their community, city or country hinders their sense of belonging and accentuates the othering process to the point of seeing politics itself as an agent of othering. The consequences of this process may be a lack of trust in government and institutions and, finally, in democracy as an institution. In our understanding, the feeling of *discrimination* is also caused by othering processes discouraging participation in civic life by erasing the sense of belonging of the discriminated. For the discriminated individual, the agents of othering could be the states that they live in, as can be the case in Hungary with the LGTBIQ+ community or the wider communities in which they partake. Lastly, *marginalisation* is an othering process, generated by the socio-political systems affecting the self-perception and self-identity of those that are othered. The othering processes fracture sense of marginalisation, and highlight different divisions such as class, gender, origin, religion, ethnicity and similar hinder belonging. In response to othering, therefore, we believe that there is a need to reconceptualise how socio-political-cultural identities can be constructed to offer more efficient approaches addressing radicalization. Boosting sense of belonging through availing shared interest and spaces can avail deradicalization.

2.3 Non-Binary Nature of Socio-Political Identities

As we stated above, we consider any type of othering as an output of a binary reading of identities and instead we advocate the idea that such approaches either miss or ignore the wider aspects of identities. Thus, we propose a re-conceptualisation of the reading of socio-political-cultural identities through non-binary lenses. Scholars who study non-binary gender identities have simultaneously captured the flexible nature of different types of identities. Thus,

we argue that their explanations can help us to understand various types of identities and their relation to the sense of belonging. Burke and Stets argue (2009) that different identities occupy different spaces in the salience hierarchy: once an identity is placed higher in this hierarchy, that identity will be more often invoked in given situations. In other words, while individuals tend to rely on different types of identities in their lives, some of their identities have more impact on their behaviours than others. For instance, one may identify oneself as a Muslim British straight woman that likes sharing new cuisines. While all these identifications may influence her decisions and behaviours in different contexts; her Muslim identity, for instance, could have more influence on her when it comes to social interaction preferences. In such a case, we can say that a woman's Muslim identity occupies a superior position in her identity hierarchy.

For some scholars, gender is among those identities that occupy a higher level in identity hierarchies (Burke & Tully, 1977). Accordingly, gender identities constitute themselves through interactions (West & Zimmerman, 1987). For those, gender represents an aspect of the self, and it is "done" repeatedly in social interactions. Hence, it is not a fixed identity category. In such interactions, social roles define who one is by reproducing themselves through the categorisations of behaviours or traits, such as masculine or feminine. This process comes from the need for societies to place gender identities into categories that are culturally intelligible to others (Hollander, 2013). This legitimises the two established sex categories and the "natural differences" among them. Thus, societies establish the boundaries that they require to govern individuals. In terms of gender, scholars state the necessity of such categorisations for political systems while they reorganize family relations for the sake of the system (Rubin, 1993). In light of these explanations, our approach argues that the processes described above also function similarly for other identities beyond gender as well including cultural, political and social identities. We follow the argument that societies create categorisations and boundaries similarly dichotomous as in gender, when it comes to spatialising other identity groups in societies as well. Through those assumptions, they establish "acceptable" or "expected" ways of being or ways of living for individuals based on their socioeconomic, ethnic or religious backgrounds. These assumptions are not non-binary by nature; rather they are strict and categorical. However, as gender scholars state, identities do not have to belong to fixed categories. Thus, in opposition to what these scholars have done with gender, we believe there is a necessity to "undo" (Butler, 2004) and "redo" (West & Zimmerman, 2009) socio-political-cultural identities as well. This can only be possible by acknowledging and embracing the non-binary nature of identities across other aspects beyond gender.

It is worth noting that people care what others think about them, and this also influences their understanding of their own identity. They imagine how others perceive them rather and their imagination may be different from how others perceive them actually (Shrauger & Schoeneman, 1979). Social relationships and social interactions in fact make one's identity (Kaufman and Johnson 2004). Goffman (1963) also points at the interrelationship between one's sense of self and social relations by saying "the nature of an individual is generated by the nature of their group affiliations." Along with this, in his influential work on stigma, Goffman also argues that individuals who belong to the group of "others" may achieve "phantom acceptance by accepting the view of the wider society about themselves" (Goffman, 1963). In any type of society, possessing a non-binary identity easily puts you in a group of others. However, even though one belongs to a group of others, there is always a transition possibility if they manage to transform themselves later to fit into a identity category that

society can accept. We see such examples in the case of transgender people (Matsuno & Budge, 2017).

Their transition may help them adjust themselves and fit into “binary ways of living” by embracing hitherto constructed gender roles. In contrast, people with non-binary gender identities could pose a deeper problem for the rest of the society; they remain as residual others, who did not “transition” to a status that the society can approve and remain permanent others. Bisexuals, and the issues that they face, could also provide a strong case to examine how societies require stable sexual identity performance (Rust, 2003) and are disturbed when individuals fail to achieve that. Bisexuals in general are thought to be lesbians or gays that are afraid to come out due to fear and bisexual women are thought to be straight but performing for the male gaze (Entrup & Firestein, 2007). Societies therefore expect individuals to be as binary as possible. This is the biggest challenge for those who have a non-binary identity, and the difficulty that binary expectations impose on non-binary people could apply to any other identity that involves similar non-binary characteristic. Our approach argues that any type of identity that contributes to resonate self/other dichotomy is one of them. In summary, societies construct boundaries for each identity during an identity creation process. This creation process involves assumptions about “other” identities similar to those related to gender.

People tend to adjust their attitudes towards others based on their assumptions about other’s identities. For instance, when someone appears as a Muslim or a person from Turkey, people that receive this information adopt it to their existing knowledge about these identities. That knowledge is mostly based on pre-constructed assumptions. Hence, people generally expect to see others fulfil their existing assumptions, such as a Muslim who does not eat pork or drink alcohol. The members of the wider societies have their own assumptions about their identities and sets of behaviours linked to those identities. All those assumptions create a binary world for everyone in it, including others of the societies with whom the wider society can feel secure whilst they remaining as residual other. One can claim that others of the societies that have identities to match the assumptions of wider society might find coexistence easier. However, as with non-binary gender identities, some people will not always fit into the sets of behaviours that are pre-constructed by the receiving society. In such cases, the individuals’ interests, which lead them into social interactions with the other members of societies, can be contradictory with their pre-constructed identities. For instance, a Muslim person might have an interest in trying new cuisines that contain prohibited dishes such as pork. In this regard, we can consider them people who have non-binary social identities that still challenge existing assumptions of themselves by the wider society.

Constructed boundaries around any type of identity do not only affect acts by the wider society, but also people with non-binary identities. Once identities are created, they are simultaneously internalized (Foucault, 1977). As Foucault explains this internalisation process using the allegory of panopticon, individuals never know if they are being watched, and they tend to moderate their actions and desires to fit into how they think they should act and how they think others think they should act (Foucault, 1978). In relation to this theory, in Nicolson and Korkut’s work (2021) on how master identity narratives, which are taken up by the receiving society, affect migrants’ self-narratives on their everyday behaviours or interpretations of their experiences. Our approach agrees with the proposition that societies designate social interaction environments, types, and ways. Those designated social interactions are always bound to cultural, religious, or national identities. Thus, they do not have space for others that potentially pose different types of living. However, because identities have a non-binary nature, the boundaries that determine the social interactions of individuals

would become blurred when it comes to their forthcoming social interactions. Thus, people who seem to have different identities can easily share similar socialisation preferences. Assuming one's social interactions are based on binary identities such as their national or religious belonging can therefore only capture a partial reality. However, when one starts to look more closely at individual identities, they get a chance to explore the real non-binary nature of identities beyond their gender identities. Accordingly, by exploring non-binary aspects of individual identities, we can establish an accurate understanding of individual social interactions. Hence, our approach will interpret its data aligned with this understanding.

In this understanding, we argue that when othering, based on binary expectations, generates a sense of exclusion, such instances may adversely affect sense of belonging and later creating potential radicalization. Therefore, societies can radicalise people if they fracture their sense of belonging. Acknowledging the non-binary nature of socio-political-cultural identities, however, could boost sense of belonging and minimize exclusion of different groups and communities. Non-binary belonging can generate more fluid categories for identities to fit in. This could be a way of tackling radicalisation as well. As we discussed above, radicalisation is fractured sense of belongingness or being excluded. To tackle this, societies must have a definition of *us* that captures as many groups as possible that constitute itself. In the following section, we will demonstrate how the conceptual discussion we posed above becomes evident in the collected WP8 empirical data in 5 countries covered.

3. Empirical Discussion

3.1 Fractured sense of belonging

The data collection methodology for each country was discussed in detail in 8.1 country reports. As we stated in our introduction, the most striking aspect of the empirical data was to see how othering has triggered similar feelings in people who experience it regardless of their ethnic, national, gender or religious backgrounds. This became particularly apparent in Poland and the UK interviews. The data in Poland was collected through semi-structured interviews with 'Więczny Raków' – a football fans association of club Raków Częstochowa. In these interviews, football fans underlined the significance of stereotypes when it comes to attitudes or perceptions of the wider society towards them. In their explanation, politics and the media have undeniable impacts on the creation of a football fan image under the name of hooliganism in society. These stereotypes developed into their othering, on the one hand, and their feeling of exclusion, on the other. Therefore, the fans in Poland stated that they are interested in politics as far as politics is interested in them, and they believed that politics was *very* interested in them.

That's probably what [...] was talking about, yes, those stereotypes. When we are stereotypically perceived as a group, you still feel certain... at least I have this feeling that I am outside this society so that society somewhere at a given moment... will judge a hooligan or something somewhere someone something mutters under his breath. Well, I don't feel connected to that person – PL1

The UK data was collected through semi-structured interviews as well with the participants of the Street Soccer Scotland – an NGO that uses football-inspired training and personal development as a medium to empower people that are affected by social exclusion or

disadvantage. When it comes to stereotyping, interviewees in the United Kingdom showed similar feelings to those of research participants in Poland. Even though their feelings of exclusion had different origins, their reflections on exclusion showed similar insights. In the way they talked about their exclusion, we have seen how a stigma about their group has overridden their individual grievances and outcasted them. Both in the Poland and the UK cases we also observed the fact that the social exclusion of such people has securitized them as well. Participants of the research occasionally raised the way they manifested themselves in social environments is perceived as a potential threat by the wider society. Relatedly, participants in the Polish and the UK cases also underlined the differences in the attitudes of security officials towards them in comparison with the rest of the society.

I'd probably say like, a lot of people kind of look down on you, as if your, like you're a no good, you're trouble, stuff like that, em, your kind of going nowhere in life. Em, and they don't really understand like your troubles or whatever. So, you're kind of labelled. There's a stigma attached when people have been through maybe addiction, homelessness, there's a bad stigma attached to that. – UK1

The feeling of exclusion can pave the way to radicalisation, and we argue that othering, regardless of its origin, makes individuals vulnerable to radical ideologies. The above examples from D.Rad data show that feelings of being stigmatized are enough to make someone feel excluded from the wider society. In such cases, individuals that feel excluded struggle to make meaningful interactions with the wider society and they might start isolating themselves from it. Relatedly, as we discussed above, radicalisation is an internal process that occurs at the individual level meaning when individuals start to isolate themselves from the wider society, they tend to encapsulate their social relations into small bubbles. In such bubbles, as the relevant literature had discussed, feelings of exclusion, discrimination or alienation can easily be abused by radical ideologies.

3.2. Convivial Experiences in Non-Binary Spaces

Even though the socio-political systems generate self-other dichotomies among different social groups, people can still make connections with each other through their cross-cutting socialization preferences such as their shared interests. Hence, we argue that radicalisation and deradicalisation research should foreground convivial experiences that individuals generate based on their extant non-binary socio-cultural identities – that are not studied thus far. Convivial culture is characterised and enabled by being mingled through everyday encounters – it is unpredictable and arises “spontaneously and organically” (Gilroy, 2005: 124). After all, everyday inter-group interactions and cultural formations have lately adopted an unspectacular and extra-governmental essence of much of the urban experience of today (Smith, 2015).

Our environment is a general cross-section of the whole society. Because it really is... There might be some... mmm... standing next to you, was it a respectable businessman, owner of some enterprise, or some street thug, right? – PL2

A doctor, or without ... homeless, maybe I exaggerated, but a doctor and a production worker can stand next to it and they will find a common language together – PL3

I'm the same, I, I felt it really welcoming, and eh... a lot ... eh... lot of people altogether when you come, and it gives you new relationships friendships that you build up and these can be friendships for life and maybe you might not have had these friendships-UK2

Hence, we propose the importance of bolstering shared spaces for (de-)radicalisation with these types of spaces offering social interaction opportunities to those that gather around a common interest. These are also the spaces that cater for non-binary belongingness with their central tenets being inter-subjectivity, togetherness, and collective understanding creation. **Such spaces are able to offer intimate experiences which can cross-cut binary identities such as nationality or ethnicity.** That is why the D.Rad project has focused on arts and sports as intervention media. Relatedly, reflections of the research participants of the D.Rad project showed how those spaces where people find like-minded others influence their feelings of inclusion as well. They underlined the fact that environments can tackle of social isolation or exclusion by bringing people from different socio-cultural backgrounds around shared interests.

Some will continue to approach stereotypically, as X said here at the beginning, while the part that has already had the opportunity to get to know us, and do something with us, has a completely different approach. – PL2

Kind of... Like kind of breaks down the, like the kind of isolation that you've had like within, like the outside world as well. Like you can isolate yourself and keep yourself away from the world. But coming down here it's just like coming down to visit like your wee Granny or whatever. Everybody knows each other, there's no judgement or anything like that. UK3

As we mentioned above, the data from the UK and Poland involves people that share the main characteristics of the majority population of their countries. However, we also observed the importance of convivial experiences for migrants as well to bolster their sense of belonging in their new countries. For the D.Rad project in Serbia, we examined the activities undertaken with refugees in Belgrade. The refugees were part of a weekly program called the 'Boys' Day' (BD) run by Info Park. This program aimed to contribute to various issues that refugees encounter in their everyday lives such as relationship building, and peaceful co-existence between groups to manage difficulties faced in their lives as outcasts and marginalized groups.

Interviewees in Serbia repeatedly suggested that friendships was the most important part of the activities for them. One of the participants (SB1), for example, stressed how important it was for them to spend time with and play football with other boys of a similar age and in a *similar position* to him. When asked if they would have been friends with these boys if they had not been to BD activities together, the same participant reported that they would not have met many of the other participants otherwise. Many of them lived in different parts of Belgrade and BD played an important role for them as a safe, neutral meeting place for other boys. Further, they stated that through playing football in a team with participants with different backgrounds, they learned how to respect other cultures. Additionally, same interviewee explained that the opportunity to share one's own thoughts and experiences on a particular topic during their gatherings enabled participants to 'learn about five cultures in one day'.

Two other research participants (SB2; SB3) also stated that weekly events helped them to make more friends outside their immediate social circles. SB2 stated that their favourite part of the BD was sitting and eating together whilst, 'talking about life' as it 'feel[s] great when we are together'. Additionally, some interviewees claimed that sports activities helped them to make connections with the local people as well. SB3 explained in the football games, it was common for other Serbian children and teenagers to join in the matches. SB3 reflected on how keen the local Serbian young people were to keep playing with the BD participants each week, which led to friendships being formed between members of the two groups. **In such examples one can see how an activity can function as a tool to gather people from different backgrounds, we interpret these activities as reflections of one's non-binary belongings.**

The data in Slovenia, collected by Zavod APIS, Street Theatre (ST) and Creative Dance and Movement (CDM), showed how activities in two artistic fields - Street Theatre and Creative Dance and Movement - became a way of expression to promote and sustain social inclusion among young people in the Ljubljana region, the capital of Slovenia. Research participants enhanced their "critical consciousness" by identifying shared identities. Particularly in the first focus group of CDM activities, a shared identity, being female in this case, forged a strong bond between them. Additionally, research participants identified themselves as having mixed ethnic origins or being a migrant. Thus, they explored their shared experiences of prejudice and injustice related to these categories during the activities and this exploration strengthened their bonds with each other. Recognising cultural and physical similarities, the participants prompted the researcher to create a WhatsApp group named "Multinational sisters". Connections extended beyond ST activities, incorporating informal conversations where they learnt each other's languages and discussed cultural similarities and differences.

In the ST group, we have seen that the overall experience they gained through the activities strengthened their self-esteem and sense of belonging. Relatedly, Interviewee 1 and Interviewee 2 highlighted the collective physical experience of creating, preparing, and performing in the public performance intervention. This experience was pivotal in fostering feelings of support and belonging to wider society. Interviewee 2 described that it made them feel "supported" by each other so that "no one was scared" and Interviewee 1 said "we became like a little family" where "everyone had a role". Interviewee 3 saw strength in the cooperation between group members during the performance and identified it as a new learning for her as they usually performed solo. It became apparent that through ST activities participants also built intimacy with each other. Interviewee 2 felt "acceptance and love from the participants" throughout the activities in the exchange. Similarly, Interviewee 5 reflected on the intimacy within the group when working with touch. They described how they learnt "how powerful is the touch" and that they did "not realise how important it is in our life". They felt that when a person in the group touched her, it was "to receive love," saying "I understand you, I am here for you, I am your friend." In a similar vein, Interviewee 8, talking about the same exercise, said they realised the intimate power of a woman's touch: "Women's touch was different. I felt appreciated. I felt loved. I felt enough."

During the Creative Dance and Movement activities, D.Rad researchers employed an innovative method to conduct a focus group. In order, dinners were organised and positioned as focus groups during the activities. By doing so, D.Rad aimed to use the power of eating

together while intimate topics were discussed. Hence, food played an important role in facilitating interactions among the women who were meeting for the first time. After the food was served and consumed, the course of the conversation ran more quickly, and the atmosphere at that time became less formal and more relaxed. The food served as a medium of conversation between them, facilitating the sharing of personal information about each other's food preferences and as a medium of cultural exchange since cultural practices and traditions were explained and shared. At the second CDM focus group, when participants were even more comfortable with each other, they also offered each other their meals to try. When they finished their meal, all participants in the first and second focus groups stayed and continued the conversation, which indicated their increased comfort in the group in both cases. At both meals, future plans were being spontaneously made among the participants. At the first focus group, the idea to connect through WhatsApp was raised. At the second focus group, plans were being made also around the food; about meeting at the next dinner when one of the participants would cook for everyone, or to come taste her food at the restaurant where she had started to work.

At the second ST focus group, the conversation about food brought humorous moments into the conversation, which relaxed participants even more. They asked to try each other's food and laughed. After the meal, these participants preferred to stay and continued the conversation. This could be interpreted as an indicator of they felt relaxed and connected to each other. In this regard, we observed the fact that eating together generated intimacy and trust among participants and importantly contributed to the creation of a safe and supportive environment for a deeper connection. The intimacy of the experience was indicated in the situation which was compared to that among family members. Furthermore, trust was built among participants eating together not only through conversations that became more intimate because of the shared experience of eating together but also through trying each other's meals. How eating together deepened the relationships was also indicated by the fact that participants started to make future plans to meet again only during or after the dinner, and not before.

The D.Rad researchers in Israel chose to examine a major netball league named "Mamanet" (association for Mothers). This association was founded in 2005. It developed and was operated by women in their local communities. The data in Israel was collected through a preliminary interview and a semi-structured group interview with netball players. The Mamanet netball network aims to attract mothers of school students (elementary, middle and high schools) to participate in weekly training. Each group holds 12 mothers connecting through their children's schools. The mother plays with a shirt bearing the name of her children's school while the teams compete against each other within a municipal league. Each team has a captain, empowering female leadership. Mamanet operates in different geographic areas and recruits women to self-sport action in peripheral regions with less access to sports facilities and women from varying demographic communities e.g., ultra-Orthodox women, women from Arab communities with patriarchal traditions, women in prisons that would not mix with each other otherwise. Most netball players live in the same locality. They shared different family statuses (single, divorced, single parents, co-parenting) and stated their diverse personal backgrounds (religious, secular, LGBTQ+) and age differences.

Participants raised some critical points during the interviews. First, all the participants claimed that sports gave them a broad contribution on a personal level, emphasising improving physical abilities, developing mental strength, and sharpening self-abilities that they were not hitherto

exposed to before they became a part of a regular sports team. Second, participants also underlined the fact that being part of the group has a broad social importance. In this respect, sports activities led participants to meet other women with different life characteristics, which helped them make new friendships. Some participants claimed they built new friendships and these newly generated intimate connections has evolved into family-like attributes with mutual trust. Thirdly, sport is perceived by the players in the team as a refuge, a kind of space that is disconnected from the daily routine allowing for release of tensions and pressures. In this way, sport was seen as a routine breaker and it produced a new act disconnecting them from the routine that they habituate as women. Fourthly, the participants considered sport as a value in itself insomuch as it instilled equality and fair competition for future generations by stationing 'sportive motherhood' as a role model.

4. Conclusion

Socio-political systems generate differences between people based on various characteristics. These created differences come with accepted and expected ways of living for the individuals who live in such societies. As we discussed above, expectations and acceptations of ways of living inevitably cause conflict among majority and minority social groups. In most cases, ways of living become the ultimate facilitator of othering for some, especially the ones who belong to minority groups. In such socio-political systems, individuals who have differences, in terms of their ways of living, turn into potential threats to social cohesion just with their existence. Thus, such individuals, as our data showed above, can easily face othering and social exclusion as a result. However, individuals not only live with their differences but also with their commoning as well. As our empirical discussion showed, people may construct welcoming environments based on their interests and such environments have the potential for collective understanding. This boosts sense of belonging and mitigates the appeal of extremism. Hence, we invite scholars who work on radicalisation and deradicalization to engage more with the mechanisms of othering and social exclusion to facilitate a deeper understanding of these issues. Hence, we propose a non-binary approach to read identities to capture people's commonalities. Along with that, we also discuss the necessity of exploration of the social interaction zones to explore the essence of social inclusion for all. Therefore, WP8 synthesis report showed that feelings of exclusion and alienation can be similar despite different backgrounds and can thwart sense of belonging of diverse communities – whether they belong to the extant self or other predispositions. The D.Rad proposal is a non-binary reading of their sense of belonging should underline how societies in fact function. Therefore, our suggestion is the construction of spaces that can liberally host such non-binary belongingness. Our arts and sports as de-radicalisation media scope has provided such spaces to emerge and foregrounded the importance of preventive de-radicalisation approaches as against securitised techniques.

5. References

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